

Implementing the U.S. Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality's Hospital 2.0 Survey on Patient Safety Culture

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Background

- Assessment of staff perceptions of patient safety culture (PSC) suggested to improve patient safety outcomes within hospital organizations
- Reduced staff perception of PSC implicated in increased incidence of clinical error rates, adverse events, readmission rates, healthcare costs, and increased patient morbidity and mortality
- Limited research regarding PSC among anesthesia departments

Problem Statement & Aims

- Currently, there is a lack of understanding of the PSC within two sister acute care facilities in Southern California.
- Assess current PSC and attitudes among anesthesia providers
- Evaluate composite measures and areas of strengths and weaknesses in perceived PSC
- Provide EBP recommendations for improvement

Review of Literature

- Non-punitive response to errors, teamwork, provider engagement, staffing, organizational learning, communication, and leadership commitment to PSC impact PSC, positively
- Validated AHRQ SOPS 2.0 tool used in PSC assessment in U.S. healthcare settings

Methods

- Design: Cross-sectional survey
- Conceptual Framework: Revised Iowa Model of Evidenced Based Practice
- Setting: Anesthesia department of two sister hospitals in San Bernardino, CA
- Sample: Convenience sample of 43 APRNs or physician anesthesiologists
- Data Collection Tool: AHRQ Hospital SOPS 2.0 survey electronically disseminated to provider's email

Results

Survey Demographics

- Total of 121 surveys distributed with 43 respondents (36% response rate)
- 37 CRNAs and 6 physician anesthesiologists

Composite Measures and Averages

- Highest composite measure: Teamwork (71% positive response)
- Lowest composite measure: Staffing and Workplace (20% positive response)

Patient Safety Rating

- When asked, "how would you rate your unit/work area on patient safety?" 49% of respondents had a positive response
- Average patient safety rating of 3.30 for unit/work area

Demographic Differences

- No statistically significant differences in perceptions between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists
- No statistically significant differences in perceptions of PSC between years of tenure

Thematic Analysis of Free-Text Comments

Staffing Shortages

- Increased workload and burnout negatively impact quality of care and patient safety
- Lead to undesirable working hours and shifts

Continuous Organizational Learning

- Staffing shortages make quality improvement (QI) processes challenging
- Collaboration with anesthesia schools can facilitate QI projects and improve patient safety

Leader Support for Patient Safety Concerns and Communication Openness

- Leaders lack knowledge of provider workflow and ignore raised safety concerns

Recommendations

Staffing, Retention, and Burnout

- Increase autonomy and skillset
- Shared governance
- Assess turnover trends/patterns/causes
- Ensure work/life balance
- Reduce workload by adequate support staff
- Build resilience with wellness interventions

Leadership Support for Patient Safety

- Shared goals and open communication
- Participative leadership
- Engage providers in QI initiatives
- Recognition of provider contributions
- PSC training and education

Implications

A more positive PSC can improve the incidence of clinical errors, frequency of adverse event reporting, quality of care, and patient safety and outcomes.

Limitations

- Single anesthesia department shared by two sister facilities study limits generalizability
- Potential bias from convenience sampling and underrepresentation of nonrespondents
- Only six of 43 respondents were physician anesthesiologists, leading to potential underrepresentation of this provider subgroup

Discussion

- Literature supports the assessment of PSC in efforts to improve patient safety
- Staffing and leadership support for patient safety are integral to PSC and interventions should be targeted in these dimensions
- Improving PSC is important to reduce patient harm and improve patient outcomes

References

